

A flow cytometric approach to define molecularly distinct EV subsets

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Abstract

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are molecularly very heterogeneous, and their characterization at the single-particle level is technically challenging. Existing approaches such as nanoparticle tracking analysis, fluorescence microscopy, and nano-flow cytometry provide important insights but often lack the flexibility to detect multiple molecular markers simultaneously. Here, we describe an optimized workflow for multiparametric EV phenotyping using a spectral flow cytometry instrument with enhanced small particle detection capacity. EVs were isolated from murine melanoma and melanocyte cell lines via size-exclusion chromatography and labeled with a fluorogenic membrane probe that enables robust, single EV detection. In this study we systematically optimized staining conditions, EV concentrations, and fluorophore combinations for a 9-color antibody panel on single EVs. We show that single-particle flow cytometry can reliably detect and resolve multiple EV surface markers simultaneously. Data analysis by unsupervised clustering further enabled the unbiased identification of distinct EV subsets, providing a practical approach for EV phenotyping in both research and clinical contexts.

Introduction

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are cell-derived membranous structures released into the extracellular space that possess well-defined lipid bilayer membranes and contain cargoes of nucleic acids, proteins, and lipids derived from their donor cell (Couch et al., 2021). EVs are released by almost every cell type and can be found in various body fluids, including blood, milk, lymph, urine, cerebrospinal fluid, and others. EVs constitute a heterogeneous group of particles characterized by their origin, size, and protein marker distribution.

Two primary subsets of EVs are exosomes and ectosomes (Welsh et al., 2024). Exosomes originate from multivesicular bodies containing intraluminal vesicles and are typically in the range of 50-150 nm in size. Ectosomes, in contrast, directly bud from the cell's plasma membrane,

typically range from 50 nm to few micrometers, and are further subdivided into microvesicles, apoptotic bodies, and oncosomes. Since it is often experimentally challenging to determine the membrane of origin for different EV populations, another way to classify EVs is based on their size. For example, small EVs (sEVs) have a diameter of up to 200 nm, whereas large EVs (IEVs) are classified as all EVs above 200 nm. However, neither classification of EVs by size nor by origin accurately reflects their heterogeneity in terms of molecular composition. In addition to the above mentioned EV subsets, other non-membranous particles like exomeres (measuring less than 50 nm, with a peak size at 35 nm) (Zhang et al., 2018) and supermeres have been identified recently (Zhang et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021), illustrating the considerable diversity within the subcellular particle landscape. This diversity in size, biogenesis and molecular composition makes the study of EVs and EV subsets highly complex and technically challenging.

Identifying EV subsets is more than a technical hurdle - it is a biological necessity. Distinct EV populations likely carry different combinations of proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids, which conceivably affect biodistribution and function (Zhang et al., 2021). In pathological conditions such as cancer, cancer cell-derived EVs have been linked to immune suppression, promotion of angiogenesis and lymphangiogenesis (García-Silva et al., 2021; Leary et al., 2022), and the creation of pre-metastatic niches (Peinado et al., 2017). Without accurately defining which EV subpopulation(s) are responsible for these effects, our understanding of disease mechanisms and our ability to use EVs as diagnostic markers or therapeutic targets remains limited.

Various techniques have been published to study EV heterogeneity at the single-EV level, including nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA), fluorescence microscopy, super-resolution microscopy (SRM), and nano-flow cytometry (Carney et al., 2025). While these methods have provided valuable insights, they are often limited in their ability to simultaneously assess multiple markers to comprehensively define molecularly distinct EV subsets.

To address this limitation, we optimized a workflow to employ spectral flow cytometry to characterize EV subsets based on the presence or absence of specific molecular markers. This

approach offers the flexibility to combine multiple EV surface markers in a single experiment and to unmix signals based on the distinct emission spectra of different fluorophores. In combination with unsupervised analysis, this method is suitable to define EV subtypes based on surface markers in an unbiased manner.

Materials and Methods

Cell culture

The murine melanoma cell line B16-F10 (ATCC) and B16-F10 cells expressing palmitoylated GFP (Leary et al., 2022) were maintained in DMEM supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS). The non-tumorigenic melanocyte cell line Melan-A (kindly provided by Prof. Jonathan Sleeman, Medical Faculty Mannheim of Heidelberg University) was cultured in RPMI 1640 medium containing 10% FBS and 200 nM phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) to support their proliferation. All cell lines were maintained at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂. For EV isolation, 10 million cells were seeded per 15 cm dish, and EVs were isolated from two 15 cm dishes per cell line. Prior to EV collection, cells were washed with PBS and cultured in medium supplemented with 1% EV-depleted FBS (Thermo) for 48 hours. As a negative control, “dummy” samples (medium without cells) were processed in parallel under identical conditions to account for any EV or particle contamination originating from FBS, medium, or plasticware.

EV isolation

EVs were isolated from cell culture supernatants following a previously described protocol (Leary et al., 2022) using a combination of centrifugation and size-exclusion chromatography (SEC). Briefly, conditioned media was first centrifuged at 700 × g for 10 minutes at 4°C to remove cells and large debris. The cleared supernatant was then concentrated to a final volume of less than

500 μ L using 100 kDa molecular weight cut-off ultracentrifugal filters (Millipore). Concentrated media was subsequently subjected to SEC using qEVoriginal/70 nm (Izon Science) according to the manufacturer's instructions to isolate EV-containing fractions. Collected fractions were analyzed for EV concentration and size distribution using nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) with the ZetaView instrument (Particle Metrix) using standard instrument settings (sensitivity – 80, shutter – 100, and frame rate – 30fps), and the total protein concentration was determined by bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay. EV samples were then stored as small aliquots in -80°C until further use.

Flow cytometry

A Northern Lights flow cytometer (Cytex) equipped with a small particle detection module was used to detect EVs using Cytex's Extended Sensitivity Performance (ESP) mode, with forward scatter (FSC) gain set to 190, side scatter gain (SSC) to 5000, and SSC-B gain to 130, enabling efficient EV detection. The SSC threshold was set to 1000. Instrument performance and sensitivity for nanometer-sized particle detection were verified using ApogeeMix beads (Apogee Flow Systems, #1527), which contain a mixture of silica and polystyrene beads ranging from 80 nm to 1,300 nm in diameter. EVs were stained with MemGlow 640 (Cytoskeleton, Inc.) and fluorescently conjugated antibodies, and acquired at a low flow rate. All antibodies with their respective fluorophores that were chosen for our study are listed in Supplementary Table 1.

EV immobilization and labeling for microscopy

EVs were immobilized and labeled as previously described (Schürz et al., 2022). Briefly, 30 μ L of EVs with a concentration of 1×10^9 particles/mL were spotted onto a microscope slide and incubated at RT in a humidified chamber for 30 minutes. Then EVs were fixed with 4% PFA for 15 minutes at RT and washed three times with 1x PBS. MemGlow was added as 1:200 dilution

in 1x PBS and incubated for 2 hours at RT. After washing three times in 1x PBS a glass cover slide was mounted using Vectashield (Vector laboratories). Slides were imaged using a Zeiss Axio Imager Z1 and images of MemGlow-stained EVs and unstained controls were equally processed for intensity adjustment using ImageJ (Version 2.16).

Data analysis

Flow cytometry data were analyzed using FlowJo (version 10). Unsupervised clustering of flow cytometry data, including UMAP and heatmap generation, was performed in RStudio (version 2024.04.1+748). Graphs were generated with GraphPad Prism (version 10.6.0). Statistical analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism. Unless otherwise specified, comparisons between two groups were assessed using unpaired two-tailed t-tests, while comparisons among more than two groups were assessed using one-way ANOVA test.

Results

Nanometer sized particles can be detected by flow cytometry

To assess the distribution of surface protein markers on individual EVs, we aimed to establish a flow cytometry-based approach using a spectral flow cytometer equipped with a small-particle detection module (Northern Lights, Cytex). To first evaluate the capability of the instrument to detect very small particles, ApogeeMix beads were analyzed. Using the instrument settings described here (see Material and Methods), we successfully resolved different bead populations, confirming the instrument's ability to detect particles within the sEV size range (100-150 nm) (Supp Fig. 1A). As the refractive index of silica/polystyrene beads differs significantly from that of natural EVs, we next isolated EVs from B16-F10-conditioned medium (CM) using SEC. NTA and BCA confirmed that EVs were enriched in the early SEC fractions, while later fractions were

predominantly composed of free proteins, indicating effective separation (Supp. Fig. 1B). For subsequent experiments, EV-rich fractions obtained by SEC were pooled.

We then sought out a fluorogenic probe to specifically label EVs independently of their surface marker expression. MemGlow™ fluorogenic probes specifically label plasma membranes and form self-quenching aggregates in aqueous solution, thereby avoiding false-positive events until they integrate into the lipid bilayer, a common problem with other lipophilic membrane dyes (Brealey et al., 2024). Indeed, using MemGlow dye we successfully labeled EVs derived from B16-F10 cells, which can be detected by both NTA and microscopy (Supp Fig. 1C+D). Importantly, MemGlow+ EVs could be detected by flow cytometry as well, whereas free MemGlow in PBS as well as unlabeled B16-F10 EVs resulted in negligible background (Fig 1A). To further validate the specificity of MemGlow to label EVs, we next utilized EVs isolated from B16-F10 cells expressing palmitoylated, membrane-tethered GFP (pGFP). As shown in Figure 1B, pGFP+ EVs were co-stained with MemGlow. To optimize EV membrane labeling, we additionally performed a dye titration. Calculating a signal-to-noise ratio based on the number of MemGlow+ events detected in EV samples vs. PBS, we concluded that a concentration of 10 nM MemGlow was best suited for our purpose (Fig. 1C).

Next, we titrated the EV concentration to identify the optimal range for flow cytometric detection and to avoid EV “swarming”. At low (1×10^6 particles/mL) to moderate (1×10^9 particles/mL) concentrations, the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of MemGlow+ events remained relatively stable, while the rate of detected events gradually increased, probably reflecting detection of single EVs (Fig. 1D, 1E). However, at concentrations beyond $\sim 1 \times 10^9$ particles/mL, the rate of MemGlow+ events suddenly dropped and the MemGlow MFI / event increased (Fig. 1D+E), indicating that multiple EVs were being detected as aggregates or “swarms” rather than as single events. These observations define an upper concentration limit for accurate EV quantification under our acquisition conditions and highlight the importance of controlling particle density to

avoid artifacts. For the remainder of this study, we used EVs at a concentration of 0.5×10^8 particles/mL, well below the swarming threshold.

Combined detection of antibody- and MemGlow-staining at the single EV level

After determining the optimal MemGlow concentration for EV labeling and the appropriate EV input, we next assessed whether we could also detect EVs labeled with individual antibodies conjugated to a range of fluorophores. To establish the optimal antibody concentration, we performed antibody titrations and again generated signal-to-noise ratio curves. Supp Fig. 2A shows the titration curve for a monoclonal antibody against CD9, a tetraspanin broadly present on the surface of many EVs, tested across concentrations from 0.125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The best signal-to-noise ratio was obtained at 0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, which was then used as the standardized concentration for all antibodies in subsequent experiments. Next, we stained B16-F10-derived EVs with the full panel of antibodies, selected to bind common EV markers (CD9, CD63, CD81) but also other surface proteins previously identified in B16-F10 EVs by proteomics (Leary et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2018), and conjugated to a range of commonly used fluorophores. Using each antibody individually to label B16-F10 EVs in combination with MemGlow, a clear signal above background could be detected (Fig. 2A). We then examined the signal intensities of each fluorescently-labelled antibody when stained with the full panel. As shown in Fig. 2B, the signal intensity of each antibody was very similar when stained individually and with the full panel. This means that EVs can simultaneously be labeled with at least 9 different fluorophore-coupled antibodies.

We next examined whether we could detect a difference in the MemGlow signal if MemGlow was applied before antibody staining or after, but found no difference (Supp Fig 2B+C). Similarly, the intensity of the antibody staining was not affected by the order of MemGlow and antibody staining

(Supp Fig 2D). These findings demonstrate that EVs can be reliably labeled with MemGlow alongside most antibody fluorophores. Taken together, our workflow allows simultaneous EV detection and analysis of up to 9 surface markers without compromising signal integrity.

Unsupervised clustering analysis of EVs from melanocytes and melanoma cells using a 9-plex antibody panel identifies distinct EV subsets

In order to apply our workflow to the detection and identification of individual EV subsets, we next isolated EVs from B16-F10 melanoma cells and non-cancerous Melan-A melanocytes. Medium controls (“dummy”) subjected to the same incubation and EV isolation steps were used to determine the particle background from FBS, culture surfaces, etc. After isolation, EV concentrations from each cell line were measured using NTA (Fig. 3A, left). As expected, B16-F10 cells released more EVs than Melan-A cells, although this difference was not statistically significant, while particle or EV concentration in “dummy” control samples remained too low for reliable detection by the NTA instrument. For EVs derived from cell lines, particle concentrations were adjusted to 0.5×10^8 particles/mL for flow cytometry. In contrast, as the particle concentration of “dummy” samples could not be quantified by NTA, fixed input volumes (120–150 μ L) were analyzed in this case. Under these conditions, a higher number of MemGlow+ events were detected in cell line–derived EV samples compared to “dummy” samples (Fig. 3A, right).

Next, we stained “dummy”, B16-F10 and Melan-A EVs with MemGlow in combination with the same 9-plex antibody panel as before. Flow cytometry data were acquired and analyzed using FlowJo, with particular attention to optimizing the compensation matrix. Initial gating based on MemGlow was followed by individual gating for each fluorescence channel to remove outlier events that would disturb subsequent analysis, and the resulting clean-gated populations were exported to R for unsupervised clustering. UMAP projection of the flow cytometry data obtained from two independent replicates for each of the EVs and dummy controls revealed 20 different

clusters (Fig 3B), characterized by individual marker profiles (Fig. 3C). We then further plotted the frequency of EVs / cluster within each sample and replicate, to identify and exclude clusters present in “dummy” controls from further analysis. As shown in Figure 3D, two clusters, 18 and 20, displayed minimal presence in “dummy” samples and therefore, these two clusters were subjected to secondary analysis to identify EV subsets at a higher granularity. To this end, we reclustered all events belonging to clusters 18 and 20, and obtained six distinct new clusters (Fig. 4A, 4B), mainly derived from the two cell lines and not the “dummy” samples, except for cluster 1 (Fig. 4C). Of note, while some clusters showed similar marker profiles, we could define four distinct EV subsets, present in both B16-F10 and Melan-A-derived EVs, that could be distinguished clearly (Fig 5): (i) CD81⁺ EVs lacking other tetraspanins (clusters 2 and 6); (ii) CD81⁺ CD63⁻ CD9⁺ (cluster 3); (iii) EVs with high staining for CD146 which also were CD81⁺ CD63⁺ CD9⁺ (cluster 4); (iv) and CD81⁺ CD9⁺ CD63⁺ EVs lacking CD146 (clusters 5).

In conclusion, our optimized workflow for single EV labeling and 9-plex surface marker staining yields new opportunities to dissect EV heterogeneity in culture media and potentially other biological fluids, enabling molecular definition and isolation of individual EV subsets.

Discussion

In this study, we demonstrate that spectral flow cytometry can be a powerful tool to profile EV heterogeneity at the single-EV level by simultaneously assessing multiple surface markers. This approach addresses a key limitation of many existing methods, including NTA, fluorescence microscopy, SRM, and nano-flow cytometry, which often lack the flexibility to combine numerous markers in a single assay. On the other hand, flow cytometry-based approaches absorbing EVs onto larger beads lose single particle resolution (Suárez et al., 2017). The ability to analyze multiple parameters simultaneously provides a more comprehensive view of EV diversity, which

is an essential basis for understanding their complex biological roles and for distinguishing functionally distinct subsets.

We provide evidence that MemGlow+ events detected by flow cytometry to a large extent were EVs. However, while MemGlow effectively labels EV membranes, it is known to also bind lipoproteins, which may lead to false-positive signals when complex biofluids are analyzed (Brealey et al., 2024). Thus, additional controls may be necessary depending on the source of the EVs under study.

One often raised concern is whether it is feasible to label single EVs with multiple antibodies, given that EVs are in the nanometer range - much smaller than cells. However, a simple calculation of the surface area of an EV with 100 nm diameter, in comparison to the “footprint” of an antibody’s antigen binding site, suggests that multiple antibody molecules can bind to EVs simultaneously, provided there are sufficient accessible binding sites. Here, we found that it is possible to label EVs with a panel of up to 9 different antibodies, without loss of staining intensity due to quenching or steric hindrance. The choice of markers we used here was based on proteomics data of small vs. large B16-F10-derived EVs separated by asymmetric flow field fractionation (Zhang et al., 2018). Thus, it was likely that at least some of these markers were distributed heterogeneously among B16-F10 EVs. We have conducted multiple controls to exclude staining artefacts, leading us to the conclusion that it is indeed possible to combine up to 9 markers simultaneously on EVs. However, careful consideration should be given to the choice of fluorophores, their brightness, and emission overlaps. Minimizing spectral overlap greatly improves signal resolution. Another important consideration in large antibody panels is to avoid bulky fluorophores, as they may hinder efficient labeling.

Applying this method to identify molecularly distinct EVs derived from melanoma cells and non-malignant melanocytes, we decided to use a very rigorous background filtration approach, based on “dummy” particle / EV isolates from culture media alone. These samples thus represented FBS-, plastic-, or dust-derived particles present in our samples. Of note, these background

controls yielded much lower EV numbers in general than cell line-conditioned media. The number of Memglow+ events detected in the cell line-derived EVs was at least 10-fold higher than in the “dummy” controls. We still exported the same number of events (10,000 per sample,) for UMAP generation across all groups. This approach ensures comparability of clustering patterns but does not represent the absolute differences in the number of events / cluster between EVs derived from cell lines compared to background controls. Nonetheless, we decided to disregard all EVs that clustered together with “dummy” events, in order to ensure that our search was limited to biologically relevant EV subtypes. On the other hand, this means we disregarded a large number of melanoma / melanocyte EVs that we could not distinguish from background events using the 9-plex panel we had selected.

Our findings suggest that, in addition to the commonly used tetraspanins, CD146 (Melanoma cell adhesion molecule) may serve as a marker to distinguish a specific subset of EVs released by melanoma cells and melanocytes. Interestingly, although Melan-A EVs did not form any distinct clusters compared to B16-F10 EVs, we still observed heterogeneity within both B16-F10 and Melan-A EVs. This heterogeneity could also be influenced by our stringent filtering approach used to exclude dummy clusters.

One limitation of our study is that we produced EVs only from two different cell lines. In future studies we aim to isolate and compare EVs from additional melanoma cell lines and to include a higher number of EVs into our analysis to represent rare subsets. Furthermore, application of this method to more challenging samples such as body fluids is pending.

Overall, our method may be broadly applicable to dissect EV heterogeneity and to expand the repertoire of potential cell type- or tissue-specific EV markers. Thereby, this approach may help to refine the characterization of pathological, tumor-derived EVs, potentially leading to the discovery of EV-associated therapeutic targets. Future work will focus on validating these markers with complementary approaches to single EV analysis.

In conclusion, with careful optimization and appropriate controls, flow cytometry can serve as a powerful and accessible tool for EV characterization. Unlike highly specialized single-EV platforms, which may require dedicated instrumentation or complex workflows, spectral cytometers are mainstay and allow rapid adaptation of multicolor antibody panels. The small particle detection module used here has been introduced and is widely available. This opens the possibility for broader adoption of high-dimensional EV phenotyping in both research and clinical settings.

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Figures

Figure 1. Detection of B16-F10-derived EVs using MemGlow. (A) Representative flow cytometry plots of PBS, PBS + MemGlow, B16-F10 EVs, and B16-F10 EVs + MemGlow. (B) Representative flow cytometry plots of B16-F10 and B16-F10-pGFP EVs with MemGlow labeling. (C) Titration of MemGlow to label B16-F10 EVs (0.5×10^8 particles/mL) compared to MemGlow in PBS. (D+E) Swarming analysis showing the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) (D) and the number of MemGlow+ events (E) across increasing EV concentrations.

Figure 2. Antibody staining of B16-F10-derived, MemGlow-labeled EVs. (A) Representative histogram plots of MemGlow+ B16-F10 EVs stained with individual antibodies as indicated. (B) Histogram plots of MemGlow+ B16-F10 EVs stained with the same antibodies as a full panel. In both cases, stained EVs (red) show a signal shift compared to MemGlow-only controls (blue), confirming successful antibody labeling. Mean fluorescence intensity (geometric MFI) values for each channel are shown beside the corresponding histograms for comparison.

Figure 3. Clustering analysis of MemGlow-labeled EVs from different cell lines. (A) Total particle concentration of Melan-A and B16-F10 EVs detected by NTA (left). “Dummy” controls were below the NTA detection limit. MemGlow+ event counts from “dummy” background controls, Melan-A, and B16-F10-derived EVs are shown by flow cytometry (right). Data represent N = 2 biological replicates per condition. Statistical significance was assessed using an unpaired t-test for NTA measurements and one-way ANOVA for flow cytometry. (B) UMAP representation of “dummy” background controls, Melan-A, and B16-F10-derived EVs labeled with MemGlow and stained with the full antibody panel. 10,000 MemGlow+ events / sample were included (N=2 biological replicates / condition). (D) Heatmap showing the expression levels of individual markers across the identified EV clusters. (E) Frequency of EVs from each sample contributing to the different clusters.

Figure 4. Re-clustering of B16-F10- and Melan-A-derived EVs after removing clusters present in background controls. (A) UMAP representation of MemGlow-labeled EVs from B16-F10 and Melan-A cell lines after removing clusters present in “dummy” background controls. (B) Heatmap displaying the relative expression of individual markers across the re-clustered EV populations. (C) Frequency of EVs in each cluster.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of EV subsets from B16-F10 and Melan-A cell lines.

Four major EV subtypes could be identified, depending on the expression of tetraspanins CD81, CD9, and CD63 together with CD146.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary figure 1. Characterization of B16-F10-derived EVs. (A) FACS plot of Apogee beads indicating the efficacy of the instrument in resolving beads of various sizes starting from 80 nm. (B) Representative nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) and bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay demonstrating EV concentration distribution and protein content across different fractions isolated by SEC. (C) Representative NTA image of B16-F10 EVs labeled with MemGlow, showing particle detection in scatter mode (left) and fluorescence signal (right). (D) Fluorescence microscopy of PBS with MemGlow as a negative control and B16-F10 EVs labeled with MemGlow.

Supplementary figure 2. Optimization of antibody staining for B16-F10 EVs. (A) Titration of anti-CD9 antibody from 0.125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ to 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, expressed as signal-to-noise ratio (EVs to PBS). (B) Representative FACS plots of MemGlow stained B16-F10 EVs, depending on the staining order. (C) Quantification of MemGlow+ events by flow cytometry, depending on the staining order. (D) Histogram plot of MemGlow+ events in B16-F10 EVs labeled with MemGlow alone (blue) or the entire 9-plex panel (orange), in both labeling orders: MemGlow first (left) and panel first (right).

Supplementary Table 1. Antibody list. A table listing all the antibodies used for flow cytometry.

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